

Circularly Polarized Photon, Statistical Approach and Maxwell's Equations

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Classically, a wave equation solution $\exp(ikx-iwt)$ follows from a tension equation for waves on a string. A similar solution $E\exp(ikx-iwt)$ and $B\exp(ikx-iwt)$ with E and B perpendicular follows from Maxwell's equation for a photon (i.e. with no photons). Neither of these solutions appears to be directly linked with a statistical approach.

We have argued in previous notes that $\exp(ipx)$ from a quantum free particle may be thought of as arising from statistical arguments. For example, $P(x) = 1$ for a free particle, but $P(p/x) = \exp(ipx)$ is an option if one wishes to consider more details. This solution allows for $d/dx P(p/x) = ip P(p/x)$. $\exp(ikx-iwt)$ leads to a Lorentz invariant argument in the exponent. For a full wavefunction $W(x)$, $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

For circularly polarized light moving in the z direction: $E = \text{electric field} = (\cos(k(t-z)), -\sin(k(t-z)), 0)$ and it seems one may link to a statistical approach because the first two components may be written as $\exp(-i(kx-wt))$ where "i" separates the x and y component. In such a case, $\exp(-i(kx-wt))$ represents a fixed modulus i.e. E , but there are internal cycling details i.e. E moves in a circle in the xy plane for fixed t . We argue that using $E \times B$ as a momentum density and the statistical idea of $\exp(-i(kx-wt))$, one may postulate the wavefunction of the photon which yields two of Maxwell's equations without sources i.e. $dB/dt = -\text{grad } x E$ and $dE/dt = \text{grad } x B$.

Wave solution $\exp(ikx-iwt)$

A wave solution may be represented by $\exp(ikx-iwt)$ which has a modulus of 1. This modulus, however, may not be of much importance for a wave because one may use the pure real part i.e. $\cos(kx-wt)$. For example, one may solve an equation involving tension to find wave solutions in strings. Maxwell's equations with no sources also lead to D'Alembertian equations for E and B exclusively, yielding $\cos(ikx-iwt)$ behaviour. Neither of these seem to make use of the modulus 1 property of $\exp(ia)$ which we have argued is linked to statistical mechanics and probability.

Statistical Approach

It is well-known that $\exp(ia)$ has a constant modulus i.e. $\exp(-ia)\exp(ia) = 1$. Thus, $\exp(ia)$ may be used to show details of internal periodic motion, even though the magnitude stays constant. If one is only interested in the magnitude, then the modulus is sufficient. (Circularly polarized light is an example.)

In previous notes, we argued that the spatial wavefunction of a free quantum particle $\exp(ipx)$ may be thought of as a statistical conditional probability. If one argues that a free particle has the same probability to be anywhere in x , then $P(x) = \text{constant}$. Internal motion such as periodic motion, however, may be occurring i.e. there may be more details to this situation. We argued

that a conditional probability $P(p/x) = \exp(ipx)$ yields $P(x)=\text{constant}$, but also introduces periodic motion and the idea that $d/dx P(p/x) = ip \exp(ipx)$ i.e. the conditional probability changes proportional to p . If one considers a Lorentz invariant expression, $\exp(ipx)$ may be generalized to $\exp(ipx-iwt)$.

In this note, we ask the question: Is there a way to link this statistical approach to photons? In the section above, a linearly polarized photon is described by an electric field:

$$E = [\cos(a), \sin(b), 0] \cos(k(t-z)) \text{ motion in } z \text{ direction } ((1))$$

There is no $\exp(ikx-iwt)$ in ((1)) and there does not seem to be a statistical scenario. B is perpendicular to E .

If circularly polarized light is considered, it seems the situation is different.

$$E \text{ circular polarization} = (\cos(k(t-z)), -\sin(k(t-z)), 0) \quad ((2))$$

Given that motion is in the z direction, the E field moves in a circle in the x - y plane, with constant magnitude. The magnitude of E (electric) field energy is $.5\epsilon_0 EE$, so from the point of view of energy, one does not need to know about rotation. It appears to be an extra detail.

One may write E in ((2)) as a 2-vector in the x - y plane or as a complex function:

$$E \text{ circular polarization} = \exp(-i(k(z-t))) \quad ((3))$$

Here the “ i ” separates the x and y components and there is a physical nature to the rotation, even though it does not change electrical energy density $.5\epsilon_0 EE$ or momentum $1/\mu_0 E \times B$. Thus, this rotation is a detail and we argue that $\exp(-i(k(z-t)))$ is of a statistical nature just like $\exp(ipx)$ in the free particle wavefunction.

Photon Wavefunction and Maxwell’s equation.

We argue that E circular polarization is $\exp(-i(k(z-t)))$ for statistical reasons. There is a degeneracy in the system which allows for all E orientations in a circle with equal probability. Imagine one only knows that momentum density for a photon is given by $1/\mu_0 E \times B$. There is a degree of freedom that allows one to rotate E and B without changing momentum density (or energy density $.5\epsilon_0 EE + .5/\mu_0 BB$). From the point of view of energy or even momentum, Energy = pc for this photon and one may also write a Klein-Gordon equation:

$$d/dt d/dt W - d/dx d/dx W = 0 \quad W = \exp(ikx-iwt) \quad ((4)) \quad c=1 \quad k=w$$

Alternatively, one may write: $i d/dt W = -i d/dx W$. This also has an $\exp(ikx-iwt)$ solution, but does not capture the physical rotation of the E field within. One may suggest that capturing the physics of the problem involves:

d/dt describes time evolution rotation AND translation in z direction describes the rest ((5))

The translation operator for motion in the z direction is d/dz . For a rotation in two dimensions,:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \cos(a) & \sin(a) \\ -\sin(a) & \cos(a) \end{bmatrix} \text{ for "a" tiny this becomes } \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + a \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad ((6))$$

Thus, (0,1) first row (-1,0) second row is the generating matrix of a rotation about the z direction. Thus, one may postulate an equation of the form:

$$d/dt \rightarrow i \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (-d/dz) \quad ((7))$$

For a circular polarized electric field given by ((2)), there will be problems with ((7)) if one considers E alone. B is perpendicular to E and may be written as:

$$B = (\sin(k(t-z)), \cos(k(t-z)), 0) \quad ((8))$$

Then, one may use ((7)) together with $E+iB$ to write the equation:

$$d/dt (E+iB) = S \cdot (-i \text{ grad}) (E+iB) \text{ here } S \cdot (-i \text{ grad}) \text{ becomes } Sz (-d/dz)$$

$$\text{And } Sz = i \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad ((9))$$

Using $\exp(-ik(t-z))$ as a statistical probability which shows internal workings or motion of E, the electric field (and also the B field) with constant magnitude, one may write an equation for $E+iB$. One makes use of the idea that d/dt represents time evolution and d/dz represents the generator for changes in z. If one writes $\exp(ipz)$, then $p=-id/dz$ so ip is a generator of translations in the z direction as well as a rotational generator.

The final result is that one may write an equation ((9)) which becomes two mixed equations in E and B. These equations are two of Maxwell's equations (which follow from experiment) for a photon (no sources). Thus, we argue that one may use ideas of probability (i.e. a statistical approach) together with a rotational degree of freedom to describe circularly polarized light and write a differential equation to describe this conditional probability broken into 2-vector form. We argue that the $\exp(-ik(t-z))$ form for $E = (\cos(k(t-z)), -\sin(k(t-z)), 0)$ is analogous to $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ for a free quantum particle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the periodic form $\exp(ikx-i\omega t)$ or $\cos(kx-\omega t)$ (real part) appears in theory of waves on a string and in the electric and magnetic fields of photons. This does not seem to imply that these theories are based on a statistical approach simply because the modulus of $\exp(ikx-i\omega t)$ is 1. If, however, one considers circularly polarized light $E = [\cos(k(t-z)), -\sin(k(t-z)), 0]$ for motion in the z direction, this may be written as a 2 vector in the xy plane or as $\exp(-ik(t-z))$. In this case, one does seem to have a statistical situation because every orientation of E (with the same magnitude) is an equally likely result. From the point of view of energy or momentum density, one only needs the magnitude of E , yet the circular motion described by the conditional probability $\exp(-ik(t-z))$ shows extra physical information. This is similar to $\exp(ikx-i\omega t)$ for a quantum particle.

Given $\exp(-ik(t-z))$ and the idea of generators of motion, one may postulate that time evolution d/dt means spatial rotation about z AND translation in z . This leads to a product of generators, one for rotation about z and one for translation i.e. d/dz . The generator for rotation is: first row (0,1) second row (-1, 0). Thus, one may attempt to write an equation, but one must use $E+iB$ for it to function, and not E alone. This implies one knows E and B are perpendicular in a photon. (They also have the same magnitude.)

$$i d/dt E+iB = i \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} (-i d/dz) E+iB \quad \text{where a circularly polarized } E \text{ (and } B \text{) are a possible solution.}$$

This equation is a combination of two of Maxwell's equations with sources removed. Thus, we argue that using circularly polarized light, one may construct a quantum type theory where $\exp(-ik(t-z))$ and its product with its complex conjugate (yielding 1) have statistical (quantum) meaning just as $\exp(ipx)$. This form is relevant because $d/dx \exp(ipx) = ip \exp(ipx)$. (Thus, one has to take the change in conditional probability $\exp(ipx)$ as being proportional to p as a relevant result.)

Thus, at least two of Maxwell's equations may have a statistical basis which is linked both to special relativity (as are all of Maxwell's equations) and quantum mechanics.